

Proactive Strategies for Teachers' ICT Competency Enhancement: Bridging Problems and Difficulties

Tuguinay, Marjorie D., Marigondon, Deborah P., Dulay, Danah Shayne P., and James, Haydee D., PhD

Abstract

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education is crucial as technological advancements continue to transform the field. This study assessed the ICT competence of public elementary school teachers in the Solano I district through a Quanti-Quali approach, employing a descriptive-comparative method for quantitative data and a descriptive approach for qualitative data. Among 111 surveyed teachers, the findings revealed an intermediate overall ICT competence, with notable proficiency in word processing and intermediate skills across ICT Basics, Spreadsheets, Presentations, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security. Younger teachers (aged 21–33) exhibited higher ICT proficiency. At the same time, no significant differences were found based on educational attainment, teaching position, or seminar attendance. Key problems included unreliable internet access, insufficient ICT training, limited access to gadgets, inadequate ICT facilities, time constraints, and skill gaps. To address these difficulties, tailored capacity-building initiatives such as workshops, mentorships, and technology integration programs are recommended to enhance ICT competence and promote effective integration into teaching practices.

Keywords: computer ethics and security, ICT basics, ICT competence, information and communication, information and communication technology, presentation, spreadsheet

Introduction

We now live in an information and knowledge-driven society shaped by major transformations in how knowledge and learning are developed. This society is characterized by its complexity, increasing globalization, and the widespread use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The integration of ICT continues to grow, particularly in education, as the field adapts to the rapid changes brought about by technological advancements. (Espinosa & Pañares, 2023) Simply integrating technology into ineffective teaching or learning practices does not automatically improve the quality of education. The presence of the latest personal computers (PCs) and software in the classroom does not ensure better learning results. Instead, it is the teaching methods and strategies that shape how technology is used in the learning environment, ultimately playing a crucial role in determining students' success (Gcu, 2020). Utilizing technology in elementary education enhanced both in-class learning and extracurricular activities, creating a positive impact on students' overall development (Zuhri et al., 2024). Thus, elementary school teachers needed to keep pace with modern advancements by developing digital teaching skills, technological proficiency, and expertise in ICT. Teachers serve as designers of learning opportunities that empower students to enhance their learning process and fully utilize their potential in active learning (Cabigas & Jadman (2023). Their expertise in information and communication technology greatly enhances their ability to manage daily school tasks effectively and efficiently, thereby contributing to quality educational outcomes (Isorena, 2022). Although ICT integration in elementary education has shown positive outcomes, various findings revealed a notable deficiency in ICT skills, particularly among elementary teachers.

Kibirige's study (2023) uncovered a significant issue among elementary educators. The research findings revealed that after the return to face-to-face teaching following the pandemic, a considerable number of primary school teachers failed to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into their lessons. Despite the growing recognition of ICT's role in enhancing educational experiences, many teachers neglected to incorporate it into their teaching practices.

Correspondingly, it was found in the study of Lacambra (2022) that elementary school teachers demonstrated minimal proficiency in software and no proficiency in hardware. Furthermore, a significant number of teachers faced challenges in effectively planning and incorporating technology into their lesson plans. The study by Larawan et al. (2023) highlighted that teacher had limited professional development in ICT. They frequently struggled with resolving technical issues and using particular ICT tools efficiently. Additionally, a considerable number of teachers indicated a lack of motivation to incorporate ICT into their teaching practices. Furthermore, the findings from Caluza et al. (2017) revealed that while teachers possess basic ICT knowledge, this is insufficient to deem them competent, as they must develop proficiency in understanding where and when to utilize technology for teaching and related tasks. Another study by Marcial (2017) indicated a need for improvement in ICT social and ethical competencies among teacher educators.

While numerous studies have examined the individual digital skills of teachers, there was a significant gap in understanding how sustainable these skills were over the long term in the ever-changing ICT landscape. Specifically, there was a lack of research on the ICT competence of public elementary teachers in the Philippines, which was vital in this era of ongoing digital transformation aimed at "quality learning." Studies have shown that incorporating ICT into education could help students develop essential 21st-century skills, but this largely depended on the ICT competency of teachers.

Thus, study aimed to determine if the profile of the respondents affected the teachers' ICT competence and the problems and difficulties encountered by the teachers in gaining ICT competence. The results of the study would serve as the basis for crafting and proposing activities to enhance their ICT skills for effective teaching.

Statement of the Problem

The study primarily aimed to assess Solano I Elementary Teachers' Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence from June 2023 to December 2024. In particular, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the profile of the public elementary teachers in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. Highest Educational Attainment;
 - c. teaching Position;
 - d. number of seminars attended on ICT;
 - e. accessibility to ICT devices; and
 - f. purpose of ICT use?
- (2) What is the Public Elementary Teachers' competence in ICT in terms of:
 - a. ICT basics;
 - b. word processing;
 - c. spreadsheet;
 - d. presentation;
 - e. information and communication; and
 - f. computer ethics and security?
- (3) Is there a significant difference in teachers' ICT competence when grouped by profile variables?
- (4) What are public elementary teachers' problems and difficulties in gaining ICT competencies?

(5) What new activities can be proposed to upgrade the ICT skills of the Public Elementary Teachers?

Methodology

This study utilized a mixed-methods design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The descriptive-comparative quantitative design described ICT profiles and identified significant differences in teachers' ICT competence based on profile variables. The qualitative descriptive design examined challenges faced by public elementary teachers in achieving ICT competence. The study was conducted in the Solano 1 District, Nueva Vizcaya, selected for its high teacher population. Schools included Aggub Elementary School, Bangar Elementary School, Bascaran Elementary School, Concepcion Elementary School, Curifang Elementary School, Dadap Elementary School, Lactawan Elementary School, PD Galima Elementary School, San Luis Elementary School, Solano East Central School- Integrated SPED Center, and Tucal Elementary School. This setting allowed for a representative sample, enhancing the reliability of findings (Gumpili & Das, 2022). The total respondents were 111 in-service public elementary teachers, sampled using proportional stratified random sampling to ensure representation across schools. The sample size, calculated using the Raosoft tool, accounted for 71% of the population, ensuring statistical reliability with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error (Hayes, 2023). The research tool of the study used various sources to complete the variables and the items. This consisted of three parts. Part 1, the Profile of the Respondents, was completed using a checklist. Part 2, Teachers' ICT Competence, included Likert-scale items rated as follows: 4 - Great Extent, 3 - Moderate, 2 - Low Level, and 1 - Not at All. Finally, Part 3, Issues and Challenges, incorporated an open-ended question.

The NICS-Basic served as the framework for assessing ICT competencies. Recognized as the foundational standard for ICT knowledge and skills in the Philippines (NICS-Basic, 2010), its skill sets encompassed ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheet, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security. Aside from the National ICT Competency Standards (NICS-Basic), the items in the instrument were drawn from the following studies: Rapid Survey on Teachers' Competencies on the Use of ICT in Teaching in Zambia by UNESCO (2020); Teachers' Competence in Information and Communications Technology (ICT) as an Educational Tool in Teaching: An Empirical Analysis for Program Intervention by Biñas and Fuente (2020); Questionnaire on Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Competencies for Secondary School Teachers by Jandi (2011); and 21st Century Classroom Teachers: Meeting the Challenge of the Digital Era with Innovation and Creativity by Abalos (2023) of DepEd SOCCSKSARGEN.

The questionnaire items from all the sources were reviewed and analyzed to select those that could be included in each skill set. Some items from one source were merged with others to make them more contextualized to the nature of the study. The statements were then transformed into a tabular format as Likert items, which were rated according to the respondents' likelihood level of performing each ICT competency. In terms of the Profile of the respondents, including age, highest educational attainment, teaching position, number of ICT-related seminars attended, accessibility to ICT devices, and purpose of ICT use, these variables were acquired from NICS 1, DepEd, and NICS 2. For the measurement of teachers' ICT competencies, the skill sets were further divided into several categories, including ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentation, and Information and Communication. Questionnaire items were grouped based on their content of differing skill sets and competencies, all oriented toward the objectives of this study. The respondents' profiles were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages to examine variables such as age, educational attainment, teaching position, ICT seminar attendance, access to ICT devices, and ICT use purposes. These analyses provided insights into their demographics, academic qualifications, professional development, resource availability, and technology integration.

The competence of public elementary teachers in ICT was evaluated using Likert scale responses for ICT skillsets, with measures of central tendency (mean) and variability (standard deviation). The mean scores were interpreted as Proficient, Intermediate, Basic, or Fundamental based on predefined ranges. ANOVA was used to compare group means, assessing significant differences in ICT competence across profile variables. Frequency, mean, standard deviation, F-value, and p-value were calculated, with qualitative descriptions provided for each group.

Results and Discussion

Section I. Demographic Profile of the Public Elementary Teachers

Distribution of Responses on the Demographic Profile of Public Elementary Teachers presents the demographic profile and ICT usage patterns of 111 Public Elementary Teachers in Solano I. In terms of age, nearly half of the respondents (45.9%) were aged 34-46, while the smallest group (22.5%) fell within the 21-33 age range. Regarding educational attainment, the majority held a bachelor's degree (56.8%), followed by a master's degree (29.7%), with only 0.9% having a doctorate. Most respondents occupied the Teacher 3 position (67.6%), while smaller proportions were in Teacher 1 (14.4%) and Master Teacher 1 (6.3%) roles, and none held the Master Teacher 3 rank. In terms of ICT seminar participation, a significant number of respondents (33.9%) had attended 1-2 seminars, while a smaller group (8.3%) had not attended any. Nearly all respondents had access to laptops (98.2%), printers (91%), and the internet (89.2%), while fewer had access to digital cameras (27%), CDs/DVDs (25.2%), or voice recorders (16.2%). ICT usage was predominantly for instructional purposes, with most teachers using technology for developing materials (98.2%), preparing lesson plans (97.3%), and computing grades (97.3%). In contrast, fewer respondents used ICT for personal or recreational activities (80.2%), writing correspondences (62.2%), or conducting research (55.9%).

Section II. ICT Competence of Public Elementary Teachers of Solano I

The overall ICT competence of the Public Elementary Teachers of Solano I, is categorized as Intermediate, with an overall mean score of 3.26. The results indicate that the teachers possess a reasonable level of competence in ICT, though further development is needed to reach Proficient levels. Among the various skill sets, Word Processing stands out with a Proficient rating, having a mean score of 3.54. On the other hand, skill sets such as ICT Basics, Spreadsheet, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security fall within the Intermediate range, with mean scores ranging from 3.06 to 3.41. These findings suggest that while the teachers are capable of performing basic to moderate tasks in these areas, additional professional development is needed to enhance their proficiency, particularly in more advanced aspects of spreadsheet management, presentations, and online communication. Overall, the teachers are equipped with essential ICT skills but would benefit from further improvement to fully integrate technology into their teaching practices.

Section III. Significant Difference in Teachers' ICT Competence when Grouped by Profile Variables

The analysis of ICT competence across different profile variables revealed a significant difference only in the age groups, suggesting that factors like generational differences or varying levels of exposure to technology might have impacted ICT proficiency. However, no significant differences were found based on the highest educational attainment, teaching position, or the number of

seminars attended. This implies that these factors did not have a direct influence on ICT competence. Specifically, ICT skills appeared to be consistent across teaching positions and educational backgrounds, while simply attending seminars was not enough to improve competence.

Section IV. Problems and Difficulties Encountered by Public Elementary Teachers in Achieving ICT Competence

This section identified and analyzed the top six (6) major problems or difficulties encountered by the Public Elementary Teachers of Solano I. The open-ended responses were clustered into themes to create patterns in the teachers' perspectives. The top six (6) problems included the following: (a) lack of reliable and accessible internet connectivity, (b) Lack of comprehensive, accessible, and effective ICT training and seminars, (c) lack of access to essential gadgets and devices, (d) lack of sufficient and appropriate ICT equipment and facilities, (e) Lack of time, and (f) lack of knowledge and skills. By analyzing open-ended responses and connecting them to relevant studies, the findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles educators face and highlight the need for targeted interventions to enhance ICT competence in education.

Among 29% of educators cited unreliable and inaccessible internet connectivity as a major barrier, echoing previous studies that highlight poor connectivity as a key obstacle to ICT integration. Similarly, 15% of respondents identified the lack of comprehensive, accessible, and effective ICT training as a critical issue, with many pointing to insufficient professional development and a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Additionally, 13% of teachers faced challenges due to limited access to essential devices like computers and smartphones, while 8% struggled with inadequate ICT equipment and facilities in schools. Time constraints were also a concern for 6% of teachers, who found it difficult to allocate time for ICT skill development due to heavy workloads and administrative tasks. Lastly, 6% of respondents mentioned a lack of ICT skills and knowledge, particularly in creating and managing digital content, which hindered their ability to integrate technology effectively into teaching. These challenges underscore the need for targeted initiatives to enhance teachers' ICT skills, especially in creating and managing digital content.

Providing educators with comprehensive training in software use and digital tools can empower them to leverage technology effectively, improving instructional quality and fostering greater student engagement. By addressing this gap, schools can ensure that teachers are not only equipped with the necessary skills but also confident in using ICT to enhance modern education.

Section V. Activities to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence

While teachers showed proficiency in word processing, they achieved only intermediate levels in ICT basics, spreadsheets, presentations, information and communication, and computer ethics and security. To address this gap, targeted activities are proposed to build teachers' ICT skills, increase their confidence in using digital tools, and enable effective integration of technology into their teaching, ultimately fostering a more engaging learning environment for students.

Table 1

Activity to Address Intermediate ICT Competence Level of Teachers in Various Skill Sets

Perceived Problems	Proposed Activities for the Enhancement of the Teacher's ICT Basics
A. Intermediate Competence in ICT Basics Skills	Activity to Enhance ICT Basics Skills of Teachers: Desktop Mastery and File Management Skills Workshop

B.	Intermediate Competence in Spreadsheet Skills	Activity to Enhance Spreadsheet Skills of Teachers: Video-Assisted Spreadsheet Training
C.	Intermediate Competence in Presentation Skills	Activity to Enhance Presentation Skills of Teachers: Creating Engaging Multimedia Presentations Training
D.	Intermediate Competence in Information and Communication	Activity to Enhance Information and Communication Skills of Teachers: Mastering Digital Communication and Resource Sharing through Peer Learning
E.	Intermediate Competence in Computer Ethics and Security	Activity to Enhance Computer Ethics and Security Skills of Teachers: Principal-Led Ethics and Security Awareness Session

I. Target Skill: Activity to Enhance ICT Basics Skills of Teachers

a. Objectives:

1. Strengthen teachers' ability to arrange and customize desktop environments for efficiency.
2. Improve navigation between drives and directories for effective file management.
3. Develop skills in zipping/unzipping files and using storage devices for file transfer and sharing.

b. Activity: Desktop Mastery and File Management Skills Workshop

Teachers will start with a workshop on organizing desktop icons, creating shortcuts, and adjusting desktop settings. Next, they will practice navigating drives and directories, organizing disorganized files into folders and subfolders, and locating specific files based on scenarios. The session continues with a hands-on activity on zipping and unzipping files and using storage devices for file sharing. It concludes with a reflection on applying these skills in teaching practices, followed by a brief quiz to assess their understanding and proficiency.

II. Target Skill: Activity to Enhance Spreadsheet Skills of Teachers

a. Objectives:

1. Enable teachers to independently learn spreadsheet skills through video-assisted modules.
2. Reinforce understanding of managing, formatting, and visualizing data using spreadsheets.
3. Build teachers' confidence in applying spreadsheet skills to classroom tasks.

b. Activity: Video-Assisted Spreadsheet Training

Teachers will be provided with a series of short instructional videos, each focusing on a specific spreadsheet skill, such as managing workbooks, formatting cells and data, applying formulas, and creating charts. Alongside the videos, they will receive a modular workbook containing guided exercises for practice. Each module will include step-by-step tasks, such as preparing a grade sheet, calculating attendance percentages, or visualizing class performance using charts. After completing each module, teachers will submit their work for review and receive feedback.

III. Target Skill: Activity to Enhance Presentation Skills of Teachers

a. Objectives:

1. Equip teachers with hands-on experience in creating and enhancing multimedia presentations.
2. Develop teachers' ability to integrate visual and audio elements effectively in classroom presentations.
3. Boost confidence in using presentation tools and equipment for lesson delivery.

b. Activity: Creating Engaging Multimedia Presentations Training

There will be a hands-on training that will guide teachers in creating dynamic multimedia presentations using tools like PowerPoint. The workshop will begin with a facilitator-led demonstration on essential skills, including customizing slide layouts, applying templates, and formatting text. Teachers will then practice incorporating animations, inserting and editing images, and adding audio or video elements to enhance their slides. They will also learn how to create charts/graphs, digital posters, and visual stories. Participants will complete a final project by designing a subject-specific presentation and presenting it using an LCD projector.

IV. Target Skill: Activity to Enhance Information and Communication Skills of Teachers**a. Objectives:**

1. Enhance teachers' ability to use web-based communication tools for collaboration and resource sharing.
2. Strengthen skills in gathering and organizing digital information for lesson preparation and classroom use.
3. Foster peer-assisted learning to increase confidence in using ICT tools effectively.

b. Activity: Mastering Digital Communication and Resource Sharing through Peer Learning

In this peer-assisted activity, teachers will pair up with a colleague to improve their ICT skills. Each pair will work on tasks like browsing educational websites, searching for teaching resources, and bookmarking useful sites. They will also help each other organize digital lesson materials, share them via email or Google Drive, and practice using communication tools like Messenger. After completing these tasks, teachers will present their work to another pair for feedback, creating an opportunity for peer learning.

V. Target Skill: Activity to Enhance Computer Ethics and Security Skills of Teachers**a. Objectives:**

1. Increase teachers' awareness of computer ethics and security issues.
2. Encourage responsible technology use and online safety.
3. Strengthen teachers' ability to handle ethical challenges like software piracy and plagiarism.

b. Activity: Principal-Led Ethics and Security Awareness Session

In this brief, principal-led activity, the principal will lead a short discussion on key computer ethics topics, such as intellectual property rights, software piracy, and plagiarism. The principal will then present a few real-life scenarios involving ethical dilemmas (e.g., handling plagiarism or online safety issues), and teachers will work in pairs to discuss and suggest solutions. Afterward, the principal will guide the group in creating a simple set of "Digital Ethics Guidelines" for the classroom, which will emphasize responsible use of technology and online behavior. The activity will end with teachers sharing one action they plan to implement in their teaching to promote ethical practices and cybersecurity. Addressing ICT competence gaps among teachers of varying age groups is crucial for fostering equitable professional development and enhancing teaching effectiveness. Given the significant differences in ICT competence observed across age groups, it becomes essential to design targeted activities that cater to the unique needs of older teachers. These activities aim to bridge the digital divide, promote confidence in technology use, and support the integration of ICT in teaching practices. By tailoring professional development initiatives to the specific challenges faced by older teachers, educational institutions can create an inclusive learning environment that empowers all educators to leverage technology effectively for improved student outcomes.

Table 2*Activity to Address ICT Competence Gaps Across Age Groups*

Perceived Problems	Proposed Activities for the Enhancement of the Teacher's ICT Basics
A. Significant Difference in ICT Competence Among Age Groups	Activity to Address ICT Competence Gaps Across Age Groups: Cross-Age ICT Mentorship and Collaboration

I. Problem Addressed: Significant Difference in ICT Competence Among Age Groups**a. Objectives:**

1. Address the ICT competence gap between younger and older teachers.
2. Offer targeted, practical support for older teachers to enhance their digital skills.
3. Promote collaboration between teachers of different age groups in using ICT tools.

b. Activity: Cross-Age ICT Mentorship and Collaboration

Following the demonstration, teachers will take part in a "Skill Rotation Challenge," where they move through different stations that focus on specific ICT tools or skills. Each station will be facilitated by a mentor who will briefly demonstrate a task, such as using an educational app, organizing digital files, or creating interactive presentations. Teachers will spend a designated amount of time at each station before rotating. After the rotations, teachers will engage in a "Speed Debrief," partnering with someone from a different age group to discuss their favorite tools and how they plan to use them in their teaching. To wrap up, teachers will collaborate to create an "ICT Improvement Commitment," setting personal goals for enhancing their ICT skills and outlining a plan for follow-up and progress tracking in upcoming meetings. In response to the pressing need to enhance public elementary teachers' ICT competence, the study identified five most critical problems identified through teacher feedback. These challenges highlight the gaps in knowledge, skills, and confidence necessary for effective *technology* integration in the classroom. To bridge these gaps, a series of targeted activities will be designed with clear, measurable objectives aimed at fostering technical proficiency, pedagogical adaptability, and sustained professional growth. Each activity will be strategically aligned with the specific difficulties faced by teachers, ensuring a practical and solution-oriented approach. By equipping educators with the necessary ICT skills, this initiative seeks to promote more dynamic, interactive, and student-centered learning environments.

Table 3*Activities to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problems and Difficulties*

Perceived Problems	Proposed Activities for the Enhancement of the Teacher's ICT Basics
A. Poor Internet Connection	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Poor Internet Connection: Pre-downloading learning materials
B. Lack of Comprehensive, Accessible, and Effective ICT Training and Seminars	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Lack of Comprehensive, Accessible, and Effective ICT Training and Seminars: ICT Integration Workshops (Curriculum-Linked)
C. Lack of Access to Essential Gadgets and Devices	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Lack of

	Access to Essential Gadgets and Devices: Tech Recycling and Refurbishment Drive
D. Lack of Sufficient and Appropriate ICT Equipment and Facilities	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Lack of Sufficient and Appropriate ICT Equipment and Facilities: Maker Spaces for ICT Learning
E. Lack of Time	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Lack of Time: Micro-Learning Modules for ICT Training
F. Lack of Knowledge and Skills	Activity to Upgrade Public Elementary Teachers' ICT Competence in Response to the Problem in Lack of Knowledge and Skills: Peer-Led ICT Learning Circles

I. Problem Addressed: Poor Internet Connection

a. Objectives:

1. Maintain a smooth flow of lessons by pre-downloading essential learning materials (videos, lesson plans, assignments) to minimize disruption caused by poor or unstable internet connection.
2. Ensure that all necessary teaching materials are available offline, reducing dependency on internet connection during class time.
3. Empower teachers to adapt their teaching methods in the event of internet disruptions, ensuring that learning objectives are still met even with poor connectivity.

b. Activity: Pre-download learning materials

Teachers will first identify and list the essential digital resources they need for upcoming lessons, such as lesson plans, worksheets, and multimedia content. Using available internet access, they will download these materials to their devices or external storage (e.g., USB drives). After organizing the files into clearly labeled folders for easy access, teachers will test the materials offline to ensure they function properly. They will then create a backup of the files on additional storage devices to prevent data loss. Finally, teachers will reflect on the benefits of this practice and discuss how it can improve teaching in areas with poor internet connectivity.

II. Problem Addressed: Lack of Comprehensive, Accessible, and Effective ICT Training and Seminars

a. Objectives:

1. Improve teachers' ability to effectively integrate digital tools into their subject-specific lesson plans, classroom activities, and assessments, enabling more interactive and engaging learning experiences.
2. Ensure the ICT workshops are tailored to each subject and align with the Department of Education's curriculum standards and goals, enhancing the relevance and impact of the training.
3. Build teachers' confidence in using technology, ensuring they feel supported in transforming their teaching practices and can utilize ICT to enhance student learning outcomes.

b. Activity: ICT Integration Workshops (Curriculum-Linked)

The workshop begins with an introduction to basic ICT tools, followed by practical demonstrations of how to integrate technology into specific subjects like Math, Science, and English. Teachers will engage in creating lesson plans that incorporate digital resources such as educational websites, multimedia presentations, and interactive tools. Participants will then collaborate in small groups to design and present technology-enhanced lesson plans, receiving feedback from peers and facilitators. The workshop concludes with a discussion on overcoming

barriers to ICT integration and a shared plan for applying the learned strategies in the classroom.

III. Problem Addressed: Lack of Access to Essential Gadgets and Devices

a. Objectives:

1. Collect and recycle old but functional devices, reducing electronic waste in the community while contributing to environmental sustainability.
2. Empower teachers with the necessary tools for digital learning, improving the quality of education and bridging the digital divide in schools with limited resources.
3. Create awareness around the issue of unequal access to ICT resources in schools and promote actions that support more equitable technology.

b. Activity: Tech Recycling and Refurbishment Drive

Teachers will be asked to bring in their old laptops, tablets, or smartphones, which will be collected, cleaned, and refurbished by a dedicated team of volunteers or IT experts. These refurbished devices will then be redistributed to teachers in need, providing them with functional tools for teaching. The drive will include a brief informational session on how to properly dispose of or donate old technology, as well as how to securely wipe personal data from devices.

IV. Problem Addressed: Lack of Sufficient and Appropriate ICT Equipment and Facilities

a. Objectives:

1. Encourage collaboration between teachers through workshops, group projects, and shared learning experiences, thereby, enhancing their ICT competencies and teaching approaches.
2. Provide a supportive space for teachers to build and enhance their ICT skills, empowering them to integrate technology into their classrooms effectively and confidently.
3. Address the lack of sufficient and appropriate ICT equipment in schools, ensuring that teachers in resource-limited areas can gain the tools and skills needed to deliver modern, technology-enhanced lessons.

b. Activity: Maker Spaces for ICT Learning

Teachers will set up a MakerSpace in the classroom or designated area using available ICT tools and materials, such as old computers, tablets, or even paper, markers, and craft supplies. The principal or facilitator will guide teachers in using these resources to create low-cost digital projects, such as digital posters, simple websites, or interactive presentations, using free online tools or apps. Teachers will then collaborate to brainstorm and share innovative ways to maximize limited ICT equipment for classroom learning, focusing on creativity and problem-solving. This hands-on approach allows teachers to utilize available resources effectively and encourages students to engage with technology in a resourceful and innovative way.

V. Problem Addressed: Lack of Time

a. Objectives:

1. Focus on essential ICT skills such as using educational apps, troubleshooting technology, and managing online classrooms, ensuring teachers can integrate these skills into their teaching practice.
2. Design interactive and focused training modules that maximize learning in a short time, making it easier for teachers to retain information and apply it in their classrooms.
3. Foster continuous growth in teachers' ICT competencies, ensuring they stay updated with the latest educational technologies and teaching methods without the stress of traditional training formats.

b. Activity: Micro-Learning Modules for ICT Training

It involves delivering short, focused lessons through bite-sized modules that teachers can complete at their own pace. Each module will cover a specific ICT skill (e.g., creating a digital presentation or managing online resources) and consist of a brief video tutorial, followed by a

quick interactive quiz or hands-on task. Teachers can access these modules at their convenience, allowing them to learn in small increments without disrupting their schedules. At the end of each module, teachers will reflect on how they can apply the skill in their classroom, ensuring both flexibility and practicality in the learning process.

VI. Problem Addressed: Lack of Knowledge and Skills

a. Objectives:

1. Promote peer learning by forming small groups where teachers can teach and learn ICT skills from each other.
2. Boost teachers' confidence in using technology in their classrooms through shared knowledge and collaboration.
3. Make the most of available resources by focusing on practical, hands-on ICT applications that work in classrooms with limited equipment.

b. Activity: Peer-Led ICT Learning Circles

Teachers will join Peer-Led ICT Learning Circles, where each teacher is responsible for learning and then teaching a specific ICT tool or skill to their peers. Teachers will first explore their assigned tool through self-study or online tutorials. During the circle meetings, each teacher will lead a short, interactive lesson on their topic, such as using a digital lesson planner, managing files, or creating online quizzes. Teachers will practice using these tools and discuss how to apply them in their classrooms. The sessions will allow for hands-on.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of this study, the following conclusions were derived: The public elementary teachers surveyed were predominantly aged 34-46, holding bachelor's degrees, and positioned at the Teacher 3 rank. Despite limited ICT training, they had high access to essential digital tools, primarily using ICT for instructional purposes, but less frequently for research or personal use.

Overall, teachers demonstrated an intermediate level of ICT competence, with word processing rated proficient and other skills, including ICT basics, spreadsheets, presentations, information and communication, and computer ethics and security, rated intermediate. Younger teachers (21-33) showed higher ICT proficiency than older groups, though ICT competence did not vary significantly based on educational attainment, teaching position, or seminar attendance. Teachers encountered significant difficulties in achieving ICT competence, such as unreliable internet connectivity, insufficient ICT training, lack of access to gadgets, inadequate equipment and facilities, time constraints, and limited ICT skills. To address these gaps, a variety of activities were suggested, including workshops on desktop mastery, video-assisted spreadsheet training, multimedia presentations, digital communication, and peer learning, as well as ICT integration workshops, tech recycling drives, and peer-led ICT learning circles.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are advanced: Firstly, to enhance teachers' ICT competence, targeted training should be implemented, extending beyond instructional use to include applications in research and personal development, with additional resources for those with limited prior training. Ongoing ICT training focused on ICT basics, spreadsheets, presentations, information and communication, and computer ethics and security should be provided.

To address competence gaps, especially among older teachers, flexible, hands-on refresher courses and self-paced online modules should be offered, alongside peer mentorship programs and in-school tech coaching. For the Department of Education (DepEd), flexible modular ICT training

courses should be introduced, allowing teachers to learn at their own pace, with allocated ICT support staff or service contracts to maintain digital equipment and resolve technical issues. Media outlets should create educational programs targeting teachers and develop curriculum materials that incorporate ICT, such as interactive lessons and multimedia resources.

Teachers should engage in micro-learning modules and self-paced online tutorials, utilizing offline resources where connectivity is poor. Finally, future research should explore age-related challenges in ICT proficiency among teachers and conduct longitudinal studies to evaluate the effectiveness of various ICT training programs.

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